

ECOPOTENTIAL

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www.ecopotential-project.eu

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ECOPOTENTIAL: Using Earth Observation to Protect Natural Landscapes

@ECOPOTENTIALprj

EcoPotentialProject

www.ecopotential-project.eu

Monitoring

Understanding

Cross Correlation Analysis: close-up

Representativeness of ECOPOTENTIAL PAS

ECOPOTENTIAL uses EO data on protected areas from Europe and beyond to understand their current and future states under anthropogenic and climate pressures and provides knowledge-based management tools

Modelling

Acting

Earth Observation for Environmental Management

The ECOPOTENTIAL Virtual Laboratory

<https://vlab.geodab.org/>

What is the ECOPOTENTIAL Virtual Laboratory?

The ECOPOTENTIAL Virtual Laboratory Platform (VLab) is a tool for facilitating the publication and invocation of scientific workflows supporting evidence-based decision-making in ecology. It allows connecting Earth Observation data and products with knowledge from experts (scientific models and workflows) for ecological studies to be used by end users such as scientists or decision-makers in protected areas.

The VLab makes data and models interoperable through data brokering and software containerization technologies

It primarily targets ecology modellers who want to port their model onto the Virtual Laboratory and hence sharing the knowledge generated in their projects.

Keywords: knowledge sharing; workflows; System of Systems; interoperability

Why a shared Virtual Laboratory?

Reliable data and sound models are the pillars for evidence-based decision-making

There is a need to support multiple programming environments and simulation frameworks for scientific model interoperability

There is a need to formalize knowledge for semantic and pragmatic data and model interoperability

How can I upload my model to the VLab? How can I get support on its use?

Contact us at mattia.santoro@cnr.it or check <https://vlab.geodab.org/>

Online documentation on the VLab is available at: <https://confluence.geodab.eu>.

The ECOPOTENTIAL Virtual Laboratory

<https://vlab.geodab.org/>

VLab technical characteristics:

- Brokering architecture supporting a system of systems approach for data interoperability
- Many programming environments and simulation frameworks supported in the VLab: Python, R, Java, etc.
- Git and other distributed version-control systems used for storing the source code of models, and launching scripts
- Docker containers used as model execution environments
- REST APIs available at: <http://vlabapi.geodab.org>
- Many Cloud platforms used for running the Docker containers: European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), Copernicus DIAS, Amazon AWS

What data and models can I currently find on the ECOPOTENTIAL Vlab?

Around 20 workflows and models can be currently accessed and run with the Vlab. Some examples: EODESM for the automated classification of land cover; IRIS_SDM for the evaluation of habitat suitability; COINS for the optimal control of invasive species and many others

What is EODESM?

The Earth Observation Data for Ecosystem Monitoring (**EODESM**) system classifies land covers and changes according to the Food and Agricultural Organisation's (FAO's) Land Cover Classification System (LCCS2) taxonomy.

It is a concrete example of a sound scientific model ported on a VLab and enabling decision-making applications.

Protected Areas Analysis Demo

References:

- Dedicated youtube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCiZvNGjFUzns5AlYpipJfdA>
- Technical Report on the Design of the ECOPOTENTIAL Virtual Laboratory: <http://www.ecopotential-project.eu/images/ecopotential/documents/D10.1v2.pdf>

Online documentation on the VLab is available at: <https://confluence.geodab.eu>.

The ECOPOTENTIAL On-Line Data Services

Key messages

Automated execution of models or modules by the users is enabled by the ECOPOTENTIAL Virtual Lab.

Users may input existing or new data and activate the online services.

Products can be downloaded in commonly used formats.

WaterMasks & LAST-EBD

Generate inundation maps with Sentinel-2/ Landsat data

inundated
non-inundated

Speckle Removal

Improved speckle suppression of SAR images to be used as input data

HydroMap & LAST-EBD

Estimate hydroperiod

Support the assessment of the hydrological cycle

WiMMed

Calculate aquifer recharge & surface runoff

WiMMed service generates maps for two ecosystem services related to hydrology

(aquifer recharge & surface runoff). Applied to Sierra Nevada (Spain) Protected Area (PA) at 90x90m for 2007-2008.

WaterMasks estimates the free open surface water extent of an area. The service applies a novel automatic thresholding methodology for separating water class areas from non-water class areas from a single Sentinel-2. Applied to Doñana (Spain), Camargue (France) PAs.

LAST-EBD generates a series of thematic raster files from a Landsat scene and more specifically the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), water turbidity, and flood mask. Generated flood masks are finally used for the hydroperiod estimation of the respective area. Applied to Doñana (Spain) PA.

HydroMap calculates the hydroperiod of a given area for a desired time-period from a series of Sentinel-2 satellite-based water masks; deriving the length of time the area remains flooded throughout a defined period. Applied to Doñana (Spain), Camargue (France) PAs.

Speckle Removal suppresses speckle in the SAR Sentinel-1 product, while maintaining the texture structure, by using guided image filtering with a good edge-preserving property.

LandMetrics

Calculate landscape fragmentation metrics

PLAND (per object)

Impact of human activities and topography on species distribution

LandMetrics calculates numerous landscape measures used as indicators of fragmentation and/or connectivity of land cover or habitat classes in a selected study area: Percentage of landscape, Total class area, Patch density, Mean patch size, Shape index distribution, Effective mesh size, Area-weighted mean patch fractal dimension. Applied to Sierra Nevada (Spain), Samaria (Greece), Montado (Portugal), Lake Prespa (North Macedonia), La Palma (Spain), Curonian Lagoon (Lithuania).

MountainMetapop

Impact of landscape topography on species distribution

MountainMetapop studies the impact of landscape topography on species distribution under climate warming by simulating the average presence of a species with certain traits in a landscape, based on spatial patch occupancy model. Applied to Gran Paradiso National Park (Italy).

The ECOPOTENTIAL On-Line Data Services

<https://vlab.geodab.org/>

Selected models and other model supportive workflows were transformed into operational online data services and integrated into the ECOPOTENTIAL Virtual Laboratory (VL). Services may be utilized either stand-alone or as workflow components to generate input for further models or decision support chains.

INSTAR provides a deeper understanding of the population dynamics of *Thaumetopoea pityocampa* forest pest and forecasts the probability of occurrence and intensity of the pest outbreaks at landscape scale, under different climate and land use scenarios. Applied to Sierra Nevada (Spain).

INSTAR

Estimate population dynamics of *Thaumetopoea pityocampa* forest pest.

COINS

Calculate optimal spatiotemporal Control of INvasive Species (tested for *Ailanthus Altissima* species).

Understanding dynamics of species distribution: human activities in support of nature

IRIS-SDM & EO-SDM

Predict habitat suitability & test the applicability of established species distribution models.

IRIS-SDM - 'Infrastructure for Running, Inspecting and Summarizing Species Distribution Models' predicts spatial distribution of suitable habitat conditions (tested with *Iris boissieri*) derived from Species Distribution Models for narrowly distributed species based on satellite-derived Ecosystem Functional Attributes. Applied to Peneda-Gerês National Park (Portugal).

EO-SDM stands for 'Ensemble modelling of species distributions using Earth observation data' and tests the applicability of established species distribution modelling algorithms (applied for rove beetles) in combination with remote sensing data applied to Gran Paradiso National Park (Italy).

COINS calculates the optimal spatiotemporal Control of INvasive Species in natural protected areas based on a routine that solves the control problem, by searching for optimal effort allocation, which minimizes invasive species density in time & space. Applied to Murgia Alta (Italy) for *Ailanthus Altissima* plant species.

PhenologyMetrics generates phenology related layers relying on NDVI time series covering a vegetation growth period. These layers include: Day at which greenup takes place; Day at which senescence takes place; Day with highest NDVI value (peak); Per pixel total number of the phenological cycles detected within the set time period. Applied to Doñana (Spain).

PhenologyChanges calculates the abrupt trend changes in the vegetation phenology cycles throughout numerous annual NDVI series. The module is based on the iterative decomposition of the NDVI time series into trend, seasonal and remainder components via using the Breaks For Additive Seasonal and Trend (BFAST) and the consequent detection of the abrupt trend changes within the trend component. Applied to Doñana (Spain).

The Earth Observation Data for Ecosystem Monitoring (EODESM)

What is EODESM?

EODESM facilitates the classification of land cover and change by simply combining environmental variables retrieved from Earth observation data.

Classifications follow the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) Land Cover Classification System (LCCS) taxonomy, and can be generated independent of scale. Changes can be detected by comparing land cover classifications for any two points in time.

EODESM has been used to classify land cover and change for a diverse range of protected areas across Europe but is applicable to any site globally as long as environmental variables are available.

The Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO)
Land Cover Classification System (LCCS) Version
2 taxonomy

Land cover classification of Gran Paradiso National Park in Italy generated using EODESM

How do I access and use EODESM?

Contact richard.lucas@aber.ac.uk or visit <https://vlab.geodab.org/>, to generate land cover classifications using EODESM (8 land cover and 64 change categories) directly from indices derived from Sentinel-2 data. Updates to EODESM and documentation are available at

<https://essilab.wixsite.com/eodesm>.

Why use EODESM?

EODESM routinely and consistently generates maps of land cover and change without the need for complex algorithms.

The environmental variables used are widely recognised and have standard units or codes. Hence, the approach is straightforward to implement and outputs are easy to comprehend.

A major advantage of EODESM is that maps can be generated for any site and have a consistent taxonomy. Land managers can therefore compare the extents of different land covers and changes that are occurring within and between protected areas across Europe.

The maps and environmental variables used for their generation can also support conservation of biodiversity and maintenance of ecosystem services.

EODESM is freely available through the ECOPOTENTIAL'S Virtual Laboratory

Keywords: land cover and change classification, Earth observation data, habitat, ecosystems.

The Earth Observation Data for Ecosystem Monitoring (EODESM)

EODESM technical characteristics:

- Generates consistent classification of land covers for any site globally based on the FAO LCCS-2 taxonomy, and uses environmental variables retrieved primarily from Earth observation data.
- Allows both thematic and continuous variables to be integrated, including those derived from time series (e.g., water or snow hydroperiod, vegetation phenology).
- Integrates additional descriptors of land covers based on environmental variables external to the FAO LCCS taxonomy (e.g., plant species, land surface temperature).
- Allows translation of LCCS classes to habitat and other land cover taxonomies.
- Detects change by comparing LCCS class descriptions and environmental variables generated for any two points in time.
- Provides an evidence-based approach to detect changes associated with pre-defined categories (e.g., deforestation, flooding).
- Attributes change to potential causes and consequences and links directly to policy and land management.
- Can integrate a wide range of environmental variables into the classification, no matter how derived, and can capture local knowledge.
- Can utilize existing local to global layers representing a diverse range of environmental variables.
- Is applicable at any spatial scale, and hence can be used in conjunction with a wide range of ground, airborne and spaceborne data.
- Facilitates comparison between any two time-separated periods but uses dense time-series to focus on specific change events or processes.
- Can be replicated with in situ data. The Earthtrack mobile App (earthtrack.aber.ac.uk) has been specifically designed to support retrieval of environmental variables and validation of land cover and change classifications generated by EODESM.
- Is simple to use, understand and implement particularly because of the requirement for environmental variables to have defined units (e.g., meters, days, °C, %).
- Is informative, utilizes ecological knowledge, and allows for targeted applications.

Example: Changes in the hydro-period from year to year (Doñana NP, Spain) can be compared to determine whether inundation or desiccation of the landscape is occurring or whether water within the landscape remains relatively stable.

Hydro-period images generated for a) 2015-2016 and b) 2016 and 2017 using Sentinel-2A and Landsat data.
c) Changes in annual hydro-period showing areas of net drying (red) and wetting (green) as alerts.

EO data products and time-series analysis for Protected Areas managers: the Protected Area from Space map browser

Protected Areas from Space map browser

ECOPOTENTIAL Protected Areas have benefited from the potential of monitoring through Earth Observation. Many bio-geophysical variables have been derived from several satellites such as Landsat, Sentinel, MODIS, RadarSat etc. Among many, users can find products such as tree cover density, vegetation height, vegetation phenology, above ground biomass, digital elevation models, soil moisture, NDVI, NDWI, Lands surface temperature, sea surface temperature, Chlorophyll-a, hydroperiod, wind fields.... The data produced is accessible and displayed through a web interface that allows easy viewing, querying, animating analysing and downloading such data or its time series: the Protected Areas from Space map browser.

Main characteristics

The Protected Areas from Space map browser functions fulfil different management needs by offering several analytical tools that will help on the monitoring and decision making:

- Visualization of each single satellite product: The legend panel shows the list of layers available and a description of the categories of each layer that can be switched on and off
- Area of interest location
- User can enhance contrast parameters and change colour palettes
- Generation of data statistical histograms or pie charts: graphical representation of the distribution of the values or categories seen in the current view
- Application of spatial filters (e.g. type of vegetation at elevation greater than 400 m)
- Complex band calculations involving more than one product such as selection by condition between two layers or layer calculator
- Animated time-series functionality
- Temporal statistics at pixel level such as mean, mode and standard deviation resulting in a new image
- Space-time analysis resulting in a 2D graph
- Detailed time evolution graph for a given point by generating time profiles of the given position
- Linked to DEIMS (Dynamic Ecological Information Management System - Site and dataset registry)

Data quality

Data quality indicators are available for those layers for which data quality has been quantified by the producer. This type of information has been carefully documented using QualityML. Essentially, producer can report the dimension of the data quality measured, the indicator used, the type of measurement done, the uncertainties used to compute the numeric result (the domain) and the statistical expression (the metrics) used to summarize it. Data usually presents quality data at product or dataset level such as reports associated to product specifications resulting in quality metrics common for the whole products or, in some cases, at pixel level. The Map Browser exposes the quality information in a dedicated window (<http://maps.ecopotential-project.eu/>). Additionally, all layers available through the map browser can be evaluated by the users through the user feedback option which is implemented using the feedback catalogue. The system implements the Geospatial User Feedback standard developed in the OGC www.opengeospatial.org/standards/guf. The user feedback allows to provide comments, ratings and questions associated to a given geospatial dataset, in this case, the selected layer.

Fig 2. Data Quality documentation based on Quality ML

Technology, Interoperability and Accessibility

The map browser is an interoperable technology resulting in a combination of a client written in JavaScript and a server written in C. It has been created using technologies that comply with international standards, namely Web Map Service (ISO 19128) and Web Coverage Service, approved by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) and the ISO. This makes it interoperable with other applications, especially with the ECOPotential Virtual Laboratory (<https://vlab.geodab.eu/>), and allows the browser to incorporate information from a variety of other servers provided by other partners in the project. It is developed by CREAL based on a previously existing MiraMon technology that has been enriched for this project and integrates the Ecopotential Data Cube (ECP - DC) (Fig.3) based on a set of Python libraries and PostgreSQL database. The ECP-DC is a system developed to easy access, manage and analyse a multidimensional cube (x, y and t bands) of Earth Observation data, so to organize and analyse long time-series.

It is accessible through maps.ecopotential-project.eu although accessibility is also available through the own client with WMS standards. The app runs on modern web browsers, desktops, mobiles phones and LGC smart TVs.

Fig 3. Ecopotential Data Cube

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- Spanish MCIU Ministry through the NEWFORLAND project (RTI2018-099397-B-/C22 MCIU/AEI/ERDF, EU).

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DEIMS-SDR as a tool to foster environmental research by providing standardised site information

Introduction to DEIMS-SDR

Protected areas not only play an important role in maintaining natural ecosystems and their biodiversity but also provide a major input into the understanding of ecosystems and their processes. Long-term monitoring for management as well as for scientific purposes is an important element in many of the protected areas. An integrated framework for documenting observation locations as well as the resulting data is often missing. With DEIMS-SDR (Dynamic Ecological Information Management System - Site and Dataset Registry; <https://deims.org>) this challenge is addressed. DEIMS-SDR is a web service that allows registering and discovering long-term ecosystem research sites and protected areas around the globe, along with the data gathered at those sites and the people and networks associated with them. DEIMS-SDR describes a wide range of sites, providing a wealth of information, including each site's location, ecosystems, facilities, parameters measured and research themes. It aims to be a globally comprehensive site catalogue of in-situ observation or experimentation facilities covering all (terrestrial) biomes and enabling that standardised information to be openly available to science, politics and the public in general.

System Architecture

DEIMS-SDR currently consists of four main components fulfilling different needs and offering linked services (Fig. 1):

- 1. DEIMS Core:** Provides a basic user interface for storing information about datasets and people and for generating respective metadata records
- 2. DEIMS-SDR:** An extension of DEIMS Core featuring additional custom-built modules that allow the storing of information about research sites, data products and sensors and the generation of ISO19139, SensorML and INSPIRE EF metadata records.
- 3. WebGIS Service:** An instance of GeoServer, an OGC compliant implementation of a number of open standards that exposes geographic information of sites as view and download services with additional rudimentary information about research sites, e.g. name, DEIMS.ID and the URL to the respective metadata record.
- 4. Catalogue Service:** DEIMS-SDR periodically loads all available metadata records into a pyCSW instance. pyCSW is a python implementation for the OGC Catalogue Service for the Web (CSW) server implementation that makes records harvestable by other systems.

Fig 1. DEIMS-SDR System Architecture

Core Features

For each site record, a DEIMS.ID is generated upon its creation. This identifier is built combining the deims.org url and an alphanumeric code and is:

- Unique
- Resolvable
- Persistent

The neutral nature of this identifier, called 'DEIMS.ID', allows cross-RI identification of research sites, thus creating more sustainable and usable site metadata records.

Interoperability

DEIMS-SDR supports a number of standardised services (WMS, WFS, OAI-PMH, CSW) for the provision of data and metadata as well as a number of metadata formats (ISO 19115/19139 and EML for dataset records, Inspire EF for site records, SensorML for sensor records). This allows DEIMS-SDR to be interoperable not only with the data infrastructure of LTER Europe, but also with DataONE and the Group on Earth Observations (GEO), as well as any other infrastructure that supports these services.

Data Products

DEIMS-SDR also allows storing information about data products. A data product is a product of a workflow (e.g. observations) that facilitates a series of datasets. In the specific case of ECOPOTENTIAL the 'data product' represents a summarised description of a series of data aimed at presenting the available data sources in a protected area without a full description of each single dataset. It should be seen as something between a broad class (e.g. biodiversity) and a detailed dataset (e.g. abundance of a species within 0.1 hectare plot). For instance, 'deposition data' can be a 'data product' that contains several parameters measured with different temporal frequencies and spatial scales. The advantage of using this approach is that instead of describing each single dataset or parameter the 'data product' can be described as a whole. The related datasets can be linked to the data product through its metadata. In this way, the protected areas as data holders do not have to document every dataset they are collecting with detailed metadata. In addition, the modellers or remote sensing experts can easily identify different types of data they can use. Once a specific datasets was identified as needed for modelling, for example, the associated metadata have to be documented by its owner.

- 1 Abisko National Park
- 2 Camargue Biosphere Reserve
- 3 Cap Corse MPA
- 4 Caribbean LME
- 5 Curonian lagoon biosphere polygon
- 6 Curonian Spit National Park
- 7 Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve
- 8 Doñana Long-Term Socio-ecological Research Platform
- 9 Gran Paradiso National Park
- 10 Hardangervidda National Park
- 11 Kalkalpen National Park
- 12 Kruger National Park
- 13 La Palma Island
- 14 Lithuanian Coastal Site (LT-04 Nagliai, Curonian Spit NP)
- 15 LTER Zöbelboden
- 16 LTsER Dutch Wadden Sea Area
- 17 LTsER Northern Negev
- 18 LTsER Platform Eisenwurzen (EW)
- 19 LTsER-Montado
- 20 Mediterranean LME
- 21 Montado in Alentejo Natura 2000 sites
- 22 Murgia Alta
- 23 National Park Bavarian Forest
- 24 Nemunas Delta Regional Park
- 25 Ohrid and Prespa
- 26 Pelagos Sanctuary
- 27 Peneda-Gerês
- 28 Réunion National Park
- 29 Samaria National Park
- 30 Sierra Nevada / Granada (ES- SNE)
- 31 Tatra Mountains Biosphere Reserve PL-SK
- 32 Tatra National Park

Fig 2. Map of listed protected areas on DEIMS-SDR

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Administrative Boundaries: gadm.org; Site locations: deims.org

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DEIMS-SDR has received funding from the following projects:

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- H2020 ENVRIplus project (grant agreement no 654182)
- H2020 eLTER project (grant agreement no 654359).
- and the ALTER-Net network

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ESSENTIAL Variables for Ecosystems: the ECOPOTENTIAL Contribution

Essential Variables are a minimal set of variables that describe a system's condition and trends by providing reliable, traceable, observation-based evidence for addressing **specific questions** and applications, including **monitoring**

ESSENTIAL CLIMATE VARIABLES (ECVs)

Atmospheric Temperature
Atmospheric Precipitation
(...)

ESSENTIAL OCEAN VARIABLES (EOVs)

Phytoplankton biomass
Chlorophyll-a
(...)

ESSENTIAL BIODIVERSITY VARIABLES (EBVs)

Species distribution
Ecosystem extent
(...)

Objective: Develop and implement a sound process to identify, select, calculate and validate the Essential Variables

7 VARIABLES USED ACROSS STUDIES AND SCALES IN ECOPOTENTIAL

Ecosystem structure
Ecosystem extent
Ecosystem function
Species populations
Species distribution
Atmospheric air temperature
Atmospheric precipitation

Locally relevant
(identified and used at PAs)

Globally consistent
(used across scales)

ECOPOTENTIAL's framework has contributed to the conceptual framework on the identification of Essential Biodiversity Variables in GEOBON.

This project has made then a direct and long-term contribution to the GEO BON Implementation plan 2017-2020.

One of GEOBON's major tasks is now the identification of Essential Biodiversity Variables.

Implementation Plan

VERSION 1.3 – AUGUST 2017
GROUP ON EARTH OBSERVATIONS BIODIVERSITY OBSERVATION NETWORK

ESSENTIAL Variables for Ecosystems: the ECOPOTENTIAL Contribution

A bottom-up approach for the identification of Essential Variables

In ECOPOTENTIAL we have suggested a system approach, where conservation managers draw on system-level knowledge and causal diagrams to identify locally important variables that meet local or sub-global needs for monitoring data.

Four steps:

- Step 1. Develop narratives to describe and identify the major system components, functions and processes, and the underlying causal relationships that affect them.
- Step 2. Develop models to quantitatively address these system elements and their changes through time using static or dynamic variables.
- Step 3. Identify the set of variables that summarize observations to operationalize the models and create the foundation for the design and implementation of monitoring systems.
- Step 4. Prioritize which observations must be collected, considering both in-situ and remote monitoring activities and the practitioners' own needs

The arrows in the Figure differentiate between direct data dependencies (full lines) and the expected causal relations between system components and essential variables (dashed lines)

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gBay: a Bayesian Network Toolbox for Ecosystem Services

gBay: an on-line platform using Bayesian Networks with geodata

To support modelling ecosystem services over space and time, we have developed gbay, an online platform where users can link their BN models with geodata, such as land cover maps or remote sensing products.

Example of a Bayesian Network for the recreation ecosystem service in the Swiss Alps.

Ecosystem services

Ecosystems provide many goods and services to society, from climate regulation, food provision, protection from natural hazards, space for recreation, and habitats for valuable species.

Mapping and modelling these services can help identify trade-offs and synergies, predict future changes, and support more sustainable planning.

Bayesian Networks (BNs)

Bayesian Networks are graphical models that are useful for ecosystem service modelling, since they:

- Can combine quantitative data with expert and stakeholder knowledge
- Visualize relationships between variables in a system and support communication
- Can account for uncertainties

gBay: a Bayesian Network Toolbox for Ecosystem Services

How to use the gBay toolbox?

Bayesian Network users can find guidelines on how to develop a BN and how to use the gBay toolbox, along with examples of ecosystem service models, data, and case studies on this wiki page:

Link: wiki.gbay.ethz.ch

Applications in ECOPOTENTIAL

Spatial BNs have been used in the ECOPOTENTIAL project for many different applications, such as:

- Analysing trade-offs between provisioning and cultural ecosystem services in the Wadden Sea (NL) and Danube Delta (RO)
- Disentangling uncertainties about avalanche protection in the Swiss Alps
- Collaborative modelling of water bird communities with stakeholders in Doñana National Park (ES). Developing scenarios of future land use change in the Sierra Nevada National Park (ES).

An example: Trade-offs between ecosystem services in the Wadden Sea, the Netherlands

The Wadden Sea is an important nursery for fish species and a resting station for a variety of wading birds, which attract birdwatchers and other visitors. The ecosystems face pressure from climate change, as well as from fisheries and pollution, resulting in trade-offs between provisioning services (e.g. fishing) and cultural services (e.g. birdwatching). To better understand this system, a DPSIR (Drivers-Pressures-State-Impacts-Responses) model was constructed, and then simplified into a Bayesian Network model that shows trade-offs between provisioning and cultural ecosystem services.

Management of Uncertainty for Ecosystem Modelling in ECOPOTENTIAL

Uncertainty in Modelling

Physically based numerical models are often used for predicting a system's future status. Such models are based on various assumptions to simplify the complex natural systems, e.g. in the input data, boundary conditions, and process parameters, introducing uncertainties and structural errors.

Reducing these uncertainties can be done by performing model calibration/validation, increasing the temporal and/or spatial model resolution, and increasing the precision of the input data.

Uncertainty propagation in system observation and decision-making

Uncertainty Estimation Methods

Various sources of uncertainty exists in numerical modelling but unfortunately no universal uncertainty estimation method is available which could be used to assess all of them. The following methods are a few examples of uncertainty estimation approaches.

Monte Carlo methods

Bayesian methods

Data based approaches

Generalised Likelihood Estimation

Probability theory

Multiple models

Sensitivity analysis

Uncertainty Quantification in ECOPOTENTIAL

Within ECOPOTENTIAL, the management of uncertainty is addressed by providing scientifically grounded measurement outcomes from numerical and statistical modelling, Remote Sensing, and in-situ monitoring.

Different methodologies and tools were developed and applied to quantify and visualize uncertainty to help Protected Area (PA) managers in their decision-making process.

Tools used to address modelling uncertainty in ECOPOTENTIAL

- Bayesian Belief Networks
- Ensemble prediction systems
- Uncertainty quantification of Remote Sensing products
- Scenarios and Serious Games
- Probabilistic risk maps
- 3-D visualization of uncertainty

Invasive Species Mapping from Multi-Temporal Very High Resolution Satellite Images: the Case of *Ailanthus altissima*

What are invasive plants species?

Invasive plants species are non-native plants able to modify diversity and functioning of ecosystems, especially when they exhibit invasive tendencies competing with native species.

Ailanthus altissima (Mill.) Swingle (known as Tree-of-Heaven), particularly abundant in Murgia Alta Protected Area (Italy), as well in both Europe and North America, is causing impoverishment in natural ecosystems with biodiversity loss and consequent economic damages.

Ailanthus altissima (Mill.) Swingle

Remote Sensing in support of alien plant detection

Remote Sensing (RS) data and techniques can allow coverage of large areas repetitively, and also provide data for areas difficult or dangerous to reach. Thus, they represent an efficient add-on or even an alternative to in-field inspections in supporting reduction and monitoring of the negative impact of invasive species on the environment. A novel study confirmed the effectiveness of multi-spectral and multi-temporal Very High Resolution (2 meters spatial resolution) satellite data (i.e., Worldview-2 (WV-2)) in the framework of a two-stage hybrid classification scheme for the mapping of *A. altissima* in the Mediterranean area as an alternative when airborne hyperspectral data, commonly adopted, are unavailable.

"Murgia Alta" Natura 2000 site. (a) Location and extension of "Murgia Alta" protected area in red line. The 500 km² analyzed area in blue line. (b) WV-2 input image, 2 m resolution, October 5th, 2011. (c) WV-2 input image, 2 m resolution July 6th, 2012. False Colour Composite: Band 5, Band 7, Band 2.

(c)

Invasive Species Mapping from Multi-Temporal Very High Resolution Satellite Images: the Case of *Ailanthus altissima*

A two-stage hybrid classification scheme for invasive species mapping

The first classification stage uses a knowledge-driven learning procedure, which can provide a multiple class Land Cover (LC) map without requiring in-field reference data. The deciduous layer extracted from this LC map will be used as a pre-filter for the input data to the second classification stage. The latter is a supervised data-driven classifier which can discriminate two classes (i.e., *A. altissima* and other deciduous) by analysing only the pixels belonging to the deciduous vegetation layer of the LC map obtained in the first stage.

A. *Altissima* invasive species mapping

The two-stage approach proposed is novel and useful since it can reduce classification complexity, time and costs involved by in-situ reference data collection. Multi-temporal VHR data and the hybrid system suggested may offer new opportunities for invasive plant monitoring and follow-up of management decision. Close-up images extracted from the final output map obtained from the July–October image pair. These images provide samples of the detection of true invasive pixels.

(a) WV-2 July and (b) WV-2 January images, False Colour Composite: Band 5, Band 7, Band 2. Deciduous plants can be observed. (c) *A. altissima* output map from second stage using the July–October image pair as input. In-field polygons of *A. altissima*, used for validation, are highlighted in magenta line.

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Management of Uncertainty for Ecosystem Modelling in ECOPOTENTIAL

Application Uncertainty Modelling in ECOPOTENTIAL Probabilistic Water Quality Prediction

In ECOPOTENTIAL, probabilistic water quality predictions have been produced for the Dutch coastal zone (North Sea), using the Delft3D Water Quality modelling instrument (<https://www.deltares.nl/en/software/module/d-water-quality/>), and compared with conventional deterministic predictions in order to assess their benefits (Meszaros, 2018).

Probabilistic water quality prediction at the Dutch coast validated against in-situ and satellite observations

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Uncertainty maps of turbidity and Chlorophyll-a concentration in the Dutch Wadden Sea and along the North Sea were produced to help decision makers for strategic planning.

Chlorophyll-a and turbidity uncertainty estimation visualization in 2D and 3D

Serious Games

An Ecosystem Service Game was developed to challenge players by simulating realistic problems of the Dutch Wadden Sea. The games encouraged discussions between participants and the exchange of information, promoted teamwork and allowed players to understand better the uncertainties that are involved in decision making.

A serious game focusing on Ecosystem Services in the Dutch Wadden Sea, developed in ECOPOTENTIAL

Impact of residential development on the life supporting capacity of the Har HaNegev arid environment - an ECOPOTENTIAL study

The ECOPOTENTIAL project in the Negev Highland demonstrated the utility of Earth observation data for conducting policy-relevant research on ecosystems at large spatial scales. Residential and associated development in the Negev Highland has had diverse impacts on a variety of ecosystem functions.

Populated areas are a major driver of vegetative cover, which in our research resulted to be the third most important determinant of vegetation productivity patterns after the environmental characteristics of elevation and slope.

The Har Ha Negev study area: (a): Location with the Israeli borders; (b): Temporal Z-score map of vegetation cover trends calculated using the Contextual Mann-Kendall significance test; (c): The Zin Natural Reserve; (d) Agricultural Farm; (e) Jailing facility; (f): livestock settlement.

Impact of residential development on the life supporting capacity of the Har HaNegev arid environment - an ECOPOTENTIAL study

Vegetative cover generally increases in close proximity to human communities (partly due to farming near these communities) and then declines rapidly after a threshold difference.

The two charts show the ratio of negative-positive temporal trends of vegetation cover change as a function of distance from the settlements' centroids: (a) ratio anomalies from zero; and (b) differences between the point ratios and the overall Har HaNegev study area ratio.

Link:

This short description of the ECOPOTENTIAL work conducted in the Har HaNegev Protected Area is featured in an interactive on-line story map which can be found at the following link: <https://unep-wcmc.maps.arcgis.com/apps/Cascade/index.html?appid=87e9f69d64e349728041200929281aaa&fbclid=IwARo6mCBUnlwom03EBOVerSkbryFT3eoCNFv2d26ohrrATR>

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Sea Surface Wind - The SARWIND LG-Mod algorithm

Why is the Sea Surface Wind (SSW) field important?

Sea Surface Wind (SSW) represents an essential variable which is important in many fields of application, such as oceanography, marine meteorology, marine oil spill monitoring and wind energy resources. Furthermore, SSW field may be crucial in the monitoring of coastal ecosystems as well as in the planning of conservation and restoration actions in marine/coastal protected areas (PAs). Due to the complex land/sea interactions which take place in coastal areas, Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) models provide reliable wind fields for off-shore areas, but their accuracy is drastically reduced in the proximity of the shorelines. Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) systems can be used to give wind information (i.e., speed and direction) at high spatial resolution in coastal areas, when favourable wind regime conditions occur.

Figure 1.
The SARWIND LG-Mod algorithm (ver. 4.01)

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What is the SARWIND LG-Mod algorithm?

The algorithm ([1]-[3]) implements a high-resolution off-shore and coastal SSW retrieval by exploiting a single co-polarised SAR image. It is uploaded in the ECOPOTENTIAL Virtual Lab.

It provides the estimation of the local SSW and of the related directional marginal error.

It is applicable when visible wind patterns onto SAR amplitudes occur.

It can provide adequate spatial resolutions (up to 4 km) and good quality estimation of the wind for marine and coastal applications.

Sea Surface Wind - The SARWIND LG-Mod algorithm

The SARWIND LG-Mod algorithm consists in:

- **Image Smoothing and Decimation.** A series of edge-preserving smoothing and decimation operations aims at both enhancing wind-induced patterns and mitigating the speckle noise of the input calibrated SAR image.
- **Local Gradients (LGs) Computation.** LGs are computed on pixel basis applying optimized Sobel operators to the resized image. All the ‘unusable’ pixels (e.g., land, artefacts, non-wind features) are previously removed.
- **Main Wind Directions Estimation.** The LG direction image is divided into sub-images (or ROIs), according to a defined spatial grid. From Directional Statistics, a confidence interval, with a fixed confidence level (1- α), is associated to the direction estimate within each ROI.
- **Reliable Wind Directions Selection.** The final step allows automatically discarding directional estimates that are considered not ‘reliable’ enough. This can be obtained by setting a suitable threshold of reliability applied to all LG-Mod outcomes.
- **SAR Wind Speeds Retrieval.** Exploiting the dependency of SAR Normalized Radar Cross Section (NRCS) on the geometry of acquisitions and wind parameters via semi-empirical Geophysical Model Functions (e.g., CMOD5.N), the inferred wind directions are used as inputs to the inversion procedures for wind speed estimation.

Figure 2. Examples of LG-Mod outputs: LG-Mod wind direction (WD, black arrows) and the related (left) CMOD5.N-derived wind speed (WS) and (right) Marginal Error (ME $_{\alpha}^{ROI}$) map (background), obtained at 12.5 km-grid, from the Sentinel-1 IW image, 5th Feb 2015. PA: Camargue (France).

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